

**Title of the article: STUDY ON PERFORMANCE OF FOREIGN BANKS IN
INDIA**

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STUDY ON PERFORMANCE OF FOREIGN BANKS IN INDIA

Abstract:

Managing NPAs should be pro-active function than a reactive response. As management of Non-performing assets has direct bearing on the bottom lines of banks, it needs highly focused and professional approach

The main objectives of the study are to analyse the impact of NPAs of Scheduled Commercial Banks, Public Sector Banks and Foreign Banks in India. The data for the present study are collected from secondary sources. Twelve years of Gross NPAs, Net NPAs, Gross NPAs as Percentage of Gross Advances, Net NPAs as Percentage of Net Advances, Gross NPAs as Percentage of Total Assets, Net NPAs as Percentage of Total Assets data from 2002-03 to 2013-14 of Foreign Banks in India been collected from the official websites of Reserve Bank of India (rbi.org.in) and various other reports like magazines, journals, published books. The data collected for the study has been analysed logically and meaningfully to arrive at meaningful conclusions. The statistical tools applied for data analysis is descriptive statistics are used.

To sum up, Compound Annual growth rate of Gross NPAs and Net NPAs of all banks under study are not less than 15.33% during the study period. They have maintained consistency in their growth since their coefficient of variation is less than one. Hence, NPAs should be curbed on war-footing otherwise, it will have disastrous effect on its survival and sustenance.

KEY WORDS: CAGR and coefficient of variation (C.V.), NPAs, Gross NPAs, Net NPAs,

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Introduction:

Managing NPAs should be pro-active function than a reactive response. As management of Non-performing assets has direct bearing on the bottom lines of banks, it needs highly focused and professional approach. Contaminated loan portfolio is definitely a bane for any bank. It puts a severe dent on the profitability of a bank where it is out of proportion. Mounting overdues are closely linked with credit management. Banking is a risky business and banks support a mountain of risk on a slender capital base buttressed by deposits taken from public. The bulk of these deposits are repayable on demand though the assets are not repayable on demand.

Due to greater emphasis on developmental and social banking, the quality of loan is affected. The quality of loan portfolio is very critical for the health of a bank. Managing NPAs should be pro-active function than a reactive response. As management of Non-performing assets has direct bearing on the bottom lines of banks, it needs highly focused and professional approach.

Objectives:

The main objectives of the study are:

1. To appraise performance of foreign Banks in terms of NPAs and
2. To provide findings based on analysis.

Research methodology:

The data for the present study are collected from secondary sources. Twelve years of Gross NPAs, Net NPAs, Gross NPAs as Percentage of Gross Advances, Net NPAs as Percentage of Net Advances, Gross NPAs as Percentage of Total Assets, Net NPAs as Percentage of Total Assets data from 2002-03 to 2013-14 of Foreign banks in India been collected from the official websites of Reserve Bank of India (rbi.org.in) and various other reports like magazines, journals, published books. The data collected for the study has been analysed logically and meaningfully to arrive at meaningful conclusions. The statistical tools applied for data analysis is descriptive statistics.

Finding/Results:

➤ **Foreign Banks In India:**

1. Foreign Banks has an Annual Arithmetic mean of Rs. 49.53 million Gross NPAs ranging from maximum of Rs. 115.79 mns. and minimum of Rs. 19.28 mns. during the study period. It has CAGR of 13% over the study period and annual growth rate/ year to year growth rate registering the highest of 125% in 2008-09 and the lowest of -30% in 2010-11. It has consistency (C.V.) of 0.61.
2. Foreign Banks has an annual arithmetic mean of Rs. 16.58 million Net NPAs ranging from maximum of Rs. 31.72 mns. and minimum of Rs. 6.39 mns. during the study period. It has CAGR of 15.33% over the study period and annual growth rate/ year to year growth rate registering the highest of 56% in 2011-12 and the lowest of -18% in 2003-04. It has consistency (C.V.) of 0.59
3. Its mean is higher than median which means that the data is right-skewed indicating most of the value is in the lower portion of the distribution. The kurtosis of 1.58 indicates a distribution that is more peaked than a normal distribution and peaked tail and caused by there are some unusually large values.
4. Gross NPAs as percentage of Gross Advances is an average of 3.2% recording the highest of 5.3% in 2002-03 and the least of 1.8% in 2006-08 during the study period.
5. Gross NPAs as percentage of total Assets is an average of 1.38% recording the highest of 2.40% in 2002-03 and the lower of 0.8% in 2006-08 during the study period.
6. Net NPAs as percentage of Net Advances has an average of 1.10% recording the highest of 1.80% in 2008-10 and the least of 0.60% in 2010-12 over the study period.
7. Net NPAs as percentage of total Assets is an average of 0.47% incorporating the maximum of 0.80% in 2002-03 and the minimum of 0.20% in 2011-12 during the study period.

Conclusion:

From the analyses it is witnessed that Compound Annual growth rate of Gross NPAs and Net NPAs of Foreign Banks under study are not less than 15.33% during the study period. They have maintained consistency in their growth since their coefficient of variation is less than one. Their Gross NPAs as a percentage of Gross Advances is not less than 1.8% and not more than 5.3% and total assets is 0.8% and 2.40% respectively.

Hence, it is concluded that NPAs should be curbed otherwise, it will have disastrous effect on their survival and sustenance.

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Chart1: Gross NPAs and Net NPAs of Foreign Banks in India

APPENDIX-1: Descriptive Statistics of Foreign Banks in India

Descriptive statistics	Gross NPAs	Gross NPAs to Total Assets	Net NPAs	Net NPAs to Total Assets
Mean	3.2	1.38	1.10	0.47
Standard Error	0.336875	0.14	0.14	0.06
Median	2.9	1.35	0.90	0.40
Mode	1.8	1.00	0.80	0.40
Standard Deviation	1.16697	0.50	0.47	0.20
Sample Variance	1.361818	0.25	0.22	0.04
Kurtosis	-0.97514	0.15	-1.44	-1.29
Skewness	0.389218	0.81	0.60	0.55
Range	3.5	1.60	1.20	0.60
Minimum	1.8	0.80	0.60	0.20
Maximum	5.3	2.40	1.80	0.80
Sum	38.4	16.60	13.20	5.60
Count	12	12.00	12.00	12.00